

Physico-chemical Studies on Phosphorylation

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Cryoscopic, ebullioscopic, conductometric and pH determinations were carried out of orthophosphoric acid alone and mixed with adenine, adenosine, creatine, glycine, asparagine, methionine, glutamic acid, urea, glucose and sucrose. The results indicate that mono-molecular complexes are formed by the interaction of phosphoric acid with purines, creatine and aminoacids in absence of enzymes and these complexes are stable even in the boiling solution.

VANOV¹ showed that intact yeast converts phosphate to organic esters. Subsequently, various sugar-phosphates were identified as intermediates in the breakdown of starch and glycogen. There exists a mechanism within the cells, whereby the free energy available from oxidation reactions are utilized to drive endergonic processes. This is accomplished by trapping this energy through the formation of phosphate compounds of high energy content. ATP and phosphocreatine, containing "energy-rich" phosphate bond as named by Lipmann², play important role in the energy transformation in living tissues as stated by Lohman³. Formation of the above compounds in animal body is aided by enzymes. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to find out a physico-chemical basis of the phenomenon of phosphorylation in absence of enzymes.

Experimental

Reagent and chemicals: Adenine (Genatosan Ltd., Loughborough), Adenosine, (Hoffmann-La Roche, Basle), creatine, glycine, 1-asparagine, dl-methionine, glutamic acid, urea, glucose, sucrose all B. D. H. AnalaR, phosphoric acid, (E Merck, AnalaR, sp. gr. 1.75) were used in these studies.

Phosphoric acid solution was standardised by estimating P_2O_5 by standard method⁴. Calculated amounts of nitrogenous compounds and carbohydrates were carefully added to 25 ml of standard H_3PO_4 solution in a 50 ml volumetric flask and the solution was made upto the mark with triple distilled water. The total volume of the mixture was 50 ml in every case.

Apparatus: Freezing-points and boiling-points of the solutions were determined with the help of a Beckmann thermometer. Conductivity was determined by Kohlrausch slide wire (Cat. No. 4258, Leeds & Northrup Philadelphia). A thermostat, fitted with a mercury-toluene thermoregulator, was used to maintain a constant temperature of 30° for measurement of conductivity of solutions. pH was measured by Beckman Glass Electrode pH Meter Model H-2.

Degree of association was calculated by applying

the equation :

$$\alpha = \frac{dt - do}{dt \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)}$$

Stability constant was calculated by applying the equation of Bjerrum, Schwarzenbach and Sillen⁵ for monomolecular complexes :

$$K_{ML} = \frac{ML}{[M][L]}$$

$$K \text{ (stability constant)} = \frac{\alpha/10}{\left(0.1 - \frac{\alpha}{10}\right) \left(0.1 - \frac{\alpha}{10}\right)}$$

concentration of each reactant being 0.1M.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results recorded in Table 1 show that when adenine or adenosine is added to H_3PO_4 the depression of freezing-point of the mixture is much smaller than the sum of the freezing-point depressions of the constituents. Further, if a calculated amount of glucose is added to the adenine H_3PO_4 or adenosine H_3PO_4 mixture, glucose depresses the freezing-point of the mixture to that extent it would, if dissolved in water alone. It is interesting to note that the degree of association, when 0.025 M adenine or adenosine is added to 0.1 M H_3PO_4 , is the same and is 0.160. Moreover, the value of degree of association and also the stability constant is maximum when H_3PO_4 and adenosine are present in the solution in 1 : 1 ratio.

The essential difference between adenine and adenosine is that the latter contains a pentose conjugated in glycosidic linkage from carbon-1 of the sugar to nitrogen in 9 position. Adenine is soluble only to the extent of 0.025 M in 0.1 M H_3PO_4 , whereas adenosine can dissolve in 0.1 M H_3PO_4 to the extent of 0.1 M. The greater solubility of adenosine in H_3PO_4 may be due to the pentose in the molecule. It has been stated¹⁰ that the energy obtained from alcoholic fermentation of glucose can produce 4 high energy phosphate bonds whereas the complete oxidation of glucose, as in respiration, can produce 30 to 40 energy rich

TABLE 1

Solutions containing 0.1M H ₃ PO ₄ and	Freezing-point depression of the mixture		Degree of association	Stability constant	Boiling-point elevation of the mixture		Degree of association	Stability constant
	Calcd.	Obsd.			Calcd.	Obsd.		
0.025 M adenine	0.281	0.245	0.160	—	0.073	0.065	0.136	—
0.025 M adenine + 0.05 M glucose	0.374	0.340	0.106	—	—	—	—	—
0.025 M adenosine	0.281	0.245	0.160	—	0.073	0.065	0.136	—
0.05 M adenosine	0.327	0.255	0.330	—	0.086	0.070	0.279	31.02
0.1 M adenosine	0.419	0.295	0.596	36.51	0.112	0.080	0.571	—
0.1 M adenosine + 0.1 M glucose	0.604	0.480	0.308	—	—	—	—	—
0.05 M creatine	0.327	0.280	0.215	—	0.086	0.075	0.192	10.66
0.1 M creatine	0.419	0.325	0.449	14.79	0.112	0.090	0.393	—
0.1 M creatine + 0.1 M glucose	0.604	0.510	0.233	—	—	—	—	—
0.05 M glycine	0.328	0.295	0.151	—	0.086	0.080	0.104	6.27
0.1 M glycine	0.420	0.355	0.309	6.66	0.112	0.095	0.304	—
0.2 M glycine	0.605	0.515	0.223	—	0.164	0.140	0.219	—
0.3 M glycine	0.790	0.685	0.177	—	—	—	—	—
0.05 M asparagine	0.327	0.285	0.192	—	0.086	0.080	0.104	10.66
0.1 M asparagine	0.419	0.335	0.401	11.56	0.112	0.090	0.393	—
0.2 M asparagine	0.603	0.490	0.280	—	0.164	0.135	0.265	—
0.05 M methionine	0.327	0.295	0.146	—	0.086	0.080	0.104	6.27
0.1 M methionine	0.419	0.355	0.305	6.50	0.112	0.095	0.304	—
0.2 M methionine	0.603	0.525	0.196	—	0.164	0.145	0.173	—
0.05 M glutamic acid	0.327	0.295	0.146	—	0.086	0.080	0.104	6.27
0.1 M glutamic acid	0.419	0.355	0.305	6.29	0.112	0.095	0.304	—
0.05 M urea	0.328	0.328	Nil	—	—	—	—	—
0.1 M urea	0.420	0.420	Nil	Nil	—	—	—	—
0.2 M urea	0.605	0.595	0.024	—	—	—	—	—
0.3 M urea	0.790	0.770	0.038	—	—	—	—	—
0.1 M glucose	0.420	0.420	Nil	Nil	—	—	—	—
0.1 M sucrose	0.420	0.420	Nil	Nil	—	—	—	—

phosphate bonds. But the results in Table 1 show that in absence of enzymes glucose does not take any part in the combination of adenine or adenosine with H₃PO₄.

In nucleotides containing deoxy-pentose, phosphorylation of the sugar is possible only at C3' and C5', since C1' and C4' are involved in the furanose ring and C2' does not bear a hydroxyl group. Adenylic acid, a nucleotide occurring naturally in yeast or in muscle, may be looked upon as adenine-ribose-phosphate or adenosine monophosphate. From the above consideration it is seen that in adenosine monophosphate or adenylic acid, phosphorylation of the sugar can take place at C3' and C5'.

Both adenine and adenosine contain the basic NH₂ group while a pentose is linked with

adenine to give adenosine. As adenine does not contain a sugar moiety, the equal value of degree of association both in the cases of adenine H₃PO₄ and adenosine H₃PO₄ mixtures obtained in freezing-point as well as boiling-point experiments can only be explained on the basis that H₃PO₄ combines with NH₂ group of both adenine and adenosine to form highly stable complex compounds which are stable even at the boiling-point of the solution. The compounds formed can be depicted by I and II :

The high values of the degree of association 0.596, and the stability constant, 36.51, in freezing-point experiments and 0.571 and 31.02 in boiling-point experiments, when the ratio of adenosine : H₃PO₄ is 1 : 1, show clearly that a remarkably stable phosphorylated compound adenosine monophosphate is formed by the interaction of adenosine with phosphoric acid in complete absence of enzymes. It therefore appears that while in living tissues adenosine di and triphosphates as also adenosine monophosphate are formed under the catalytic action of enzymes only adenosine monophosphate, having the formula shown above, is formed *in vitro* in absence of enzymes.

When creatine is added to H₃PO₄ the freezing-point depression of the mixture is much smaller than the sum of the freezing-point depressions of the constituents. However, glucose added to a mixture of H₃PO₄ and creatine lowers the freezing-point of the resultant mixture to the extent it would do if dissolved in water alone. The degree of association

as well as the stability constant value is maximum when the ratio of H_3PO_4 : creatine is 1 : 1 indicating that monomolecular complex phosphocreatine is formed. The boiling-point experiment results show that phosphocreatine is stable even in boiling solution. The formula of phosphocreatine formed *in vitro* is

III

The formation of phosphocreatine and its hydrolysis to creatine and phosphoric acid readily occur in muscle aided by an enzyme. But results in Table 1 show that creatine and H_3PO_4 form stable complex in complete absence of enzymes and glucose does not contribute any energy to the formation of this complex although biologists state that in living systems, the energy obtained by the oxidation of glucose or other metabolites under the influence of enzymes are necessary for the formation of phosphocreatine and ATP.

When glycine, asparagine, methionine or glutamic acid is added to H_3PO_4 , the freezing-point depression of the mixture in each case is much smaller than the sum of the freezing-point depressions of the constituents. Moreover, the degree of association is maximum when the ratio of H_3PO_4 : amino acid is 1 : 1. The boiling point experiment results are in agreement with the freezing-point data. The results indicate the formation of monomolecular complexes of amino acids with phosphoric acid which are stable even in boiling solution. The complexes may be represented as shown below :

IV

V

VI

VII

VIII

When urea, glucose and sucrose are added to H_3PO_4 , the freezing-point depression of the mixture is equal to the sum of the freezing-point depressions of the constituents when the ratio of the reacting substances is 1 : 1. But in the case of urea, the

freezing-point of the mixture is slightly smaller than the additive values when the ratio of urea : H_3PO_4 is 2 : 1 or 3 : 1. These results indicate that although urea contains two NH_2 groups its complex formation tendency with H_3PO_4 is not pronounced and glucose and sucrose do not combine with H_3PO_4 *in vitro* in absence of enzymes.

Results in Table 2 show that when adenine or adenosine is added to H_3PO_4 there is a marked decrease in the specific conductance of the acid. Moreover, the percent decrease in the specific conductance is the same in both the cases when 0.025 M adenine or adenosine is added to 0.1 M H_3PO_4 . If glucose is added to a mixture containing adenine and H_3PO_4 or adenosine and H_3PO_4 , a slight decrease in the specific conductance of the mixture is observed. The fall in the specific conductance of H_3PO_4 is maximum when the ratio of adenosine : H_3PO_4 is 1 : 1. These results are in agreement with the freezing-point and boiling-point data.

A marked decrease in the specific conductance of the acid is observed in every case when creatine, glycine, asparagine, methionine or glutamic acid is added to H_3PO_4 . The fall in conductivity is maximum when the ratio of creatine or amino acid : H_3PO_4 is 1 : 1. But if excess of creatine or amino acid is added, the corresponding decrease in specific conductance is small showing that monomolecular complexes are formed by the interaction of H_3PO_4 with creatine or amino acid. These results are in agreement with freezing-point and boiling-point data.

When urea is added to H_3PO_4 , a fall in specific conductance is observed but the percent decrease is much smaller compared to purines, creatine and amino acid at comparable concentration. This also shows that complex formation tendency of urea is less pronounced.

Table 2 shows that when adenine or adenosine is added to H_3PO_4 there is a marked increase in pH of the acid and if 0.025 M adenine or adenosine is added to H_3PO_4 the increase in pH is the same in both the cases. Moreover, when glucose is added to the mixture containing adenine and H_3PO_4 or adenosine and H_3PO_4 the pH of the mixture does not change at all. Similarly when creatine is added to H_3PO_4 a marked increase in pH is observed and if glucose is added to the mixture containing creatine and H_3PO_4 , the pH of the mixture does not change. A marked increase in pH is also observed in every case when glycine, asparagine, methionine or glutamic acid is added to H_3PO_4 . When the ratio of adenosine or creatine or amino acid : H_3PO_4 is 1 : 1 the change in pH is maximum showing that monomolecular complexes are formed by the interaction of purines, creatine or amino acids and H_3PO_4 . Thus, pH results are also in agreement with freezing-point, boiling-point and conductivity data.

When urea, glucose or sucrose is added to H_3PO_4 the pH of the acid does not change showing that urea and carbohydrates do not form complex with H_3PO_4 .

TABLE 2

Solutions containing 0.1 M H ₃ PO ₄ and	Specific conductance at 30°	% Decrease	pH	% Decrease in H ion conc.
0.025 M adenine	0.00759	32.35	1.90	49.80
0.025 M adenine + 0.05 M glucose	0.00752	32.97	1.90	49.80
0.025 M adenosine	0.00759	32.35	1.90	49.80
0.05 M adenosine	0.00564	49.73	2.15	71.79
0.05 M adenosine + 0.05 M glucose	0.00557	50.35	2.15	71.79
0.075 M adenosine	0.00484	56.86	2.45	85.85
0.1 M adenosine	0.00444	60.43	2.70	92.03
0.1 M adenosine + 0.1 M glucose	0.00430	61.67	2.70	92.03
0.05 M creatine	0.00692	38.32	1.95	55.38
0.05 M creatine + 0.05 M glucose	0.00672	40.10	1.95	55.38
0.1 M creatine	0.00564	49.73	2.25	77.57
0.1 M creatine + 0.1 M glucose	0.00537	52.14	2.25	77.57
0.05 M glycine	0.00726	35.29	1.90	49.80
0.1 M glycine	0.00625	44.30	2.15	84.14
0.2 M glycine	0.00591	47.32	2.40	88.76
0.3 M glycine	0.00591	47.32	2.55	43.82
0.05 M asparagine	0.00712	36.54	1.85	68.36
0.1 M asparagine	0.00591	47.32	2.10	80.00
0.2 M asparagine	0.00524	53.29	2.30	43.82
0.05 M methionine	0.00699	37.30	1.85	68.36
0.1 M methionine	0.00578	48.48	2.10	82.18
0.2 M methionine	0.00497	55.70	2.35	43.82
0.05 M glutamic acid	0.00705	31.76	1.85	68.36
0.1 M glutamic acid	0.00578	48.48	2.10	Nil
0.1 M urea	0.01068	4.81	1.60	Nil
0.2 M urea	0.00442	6.95	1.60	Nil
0.3 M urea	0.00108	10.16	1.60	Nil
0.1 M glucose	—	—	1.60	Nil
0.1 M sucrose	—	—	1.60	Nil

An overall examination of the experimental results of freezing point depression, boiling-point elevation, specific conductance and pH shows definitely that remarkably stable monomolecular complexes viz. adenine monophosphate, adenosine monophosphate, phosphocreatine and monophosphates of glycine, asparagine, methionine or glutamic acid are formed by the interaction of H₃PO₄ with purines, creatine and amino acids *in vitro* and in complete absence of enzymes. These complexes are stable even in boiling solution. Thus a physico-chemical basis of the phenomenon of phosphorylation has been substantiated by cryoscopic, ebullioscopic, conductometric and pH determinations.

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